

New Data Spaces for Green Mobility

Huge amounts of mobility data are collected by an increasing number of ubiquitous sensors.

MobiSpaces will develop effective **data governance solutions** to exploit the huge data volumes produced in secure and trustworthy digital infrastructures.

Enabling **data sharing, reuse and interoperability** using standardised protocols across stakeholders and **minimising its environmental footprint**.

The MobiSpaces Technologies

MobiSpaces delivers an **end-to-end mobility-aware and optimised data governance platform**. Using AI-based mobility analytics to **optimise the complete data path** and increase energy efficiency contributing to the **European green transition**.

AI-based Data Operations Toolbox

Declarative Querying

Decentralized Data Management

Online Data Aggregator

Edge Analytics Suite

XAI Prediction Modelling

Edge-driven Federated Learning

Visual Analytics

MobiSpaces Use Cases

Five mobility use cases from the urban and maritime domains will show the impact of the MobiSpaces technologies on real life scenarios.

iRoute
Intelligent Public Transport Routing

SmartSense
Intelligent Infrastructure Traffic Sensing

MarineTrafficTracker
Edge-powered Vessel Tracking

OpenSeaMap
Federated Learning for Enhancing Nautical Charts

VesselEdge
Edge Computing Onboard of Moving Vessels

MobiSpaces Consortium

25 partners will be joining efforts in the Horizon Europe project MobiSpaces, coordinated by GFT, from September 2022 to August 2025.

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